

EMERGENCE OF AGGRESSION AND NEGATIVISM IN PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENT PERIOD.

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Abstract: This article explains the change in behavior, the appearance of negative characteristics, the formation of interpersonal relationships caused by disagreements between people, aggression in adolescence.

Key words: aggressiveness, aggressive behavior, negativity, anger, anger, hatred, disagreement, intensity, aggression, emotion, improper upbringing, psychological characteristics and biological characteristics in adolescence.

Introduction: In everyday life, aggression is perceived by people as a purely negative manifestation of human nature. The concept of this phenomenon and its description in clinical psychology and psychiatry also have a negative meaning. This includes destruction, damage, physical and mental suffering. According to accepted formulas, aggression is actions and statements aimed at harming another being, causing mental and physical pain.

At the same time, the word "aggression" itself (from the Greek. "Agredi") means "going forward", "approaching". the problem of personal aggression is relevant throughout the existence of mankind. Because it affects everyone and is the cause of many disasters and crimes. Aggressive behavior during the life of a teenager is characteristic of a person who is not easy to overcome. Coping with these aggressive impulses is important for building social bonds and personal well-being. Therefore, the problem of personality aggression is particularly relevant, comes to the fore in scientific understanding, and its further study is unquestionable. Adolescence is a favorable period for the formation of a person's self-esteem, because a person's self-control leads to an increase in physical and mental health and self-awareness as a full member of society. will help.

Analysis of literature on the topic:

The problem of aggression has been researched in different directions in psychology, and there are different approaches to the concept of aggression. H. Delgado, A. A. Bass, L. M. Semenyuk, G. Parens, A. Bandura, R. Walters, Yu. Mozhginsky, aggression as a negative emotional state of a person is evaluated. There are also positive approaches to aggression. In particular, L. Bender defines aggression as a person's desire for self-expression, from the point of view of motivation, R. Beron D. Richardson's aggression is intentional harm to the victim, L. Bender divides aggression into voluntary and instrumental types. Among the Uzbek psychologists, G. B. Shoumarov, Z. T. Nishanova, B. M. Umarov, U. D. Kadirov research aggression as a behavior and consider it mainly as a result of upbringing during adolescence.

Research methodology: (Methodology issledovaniya:)

In the field of psychology, to theoretically study the research of the psychological characteristics of the elimination of personal aggression. To analyze the types and causes of

origin in the research of the psychological characteristics of the elimination of personal aggression.

Adolescent aggression is considered one of the acute problems not only for pedagogues and psychologists, but also for the whole society. Today, the increasing number of aggressive children is considered an urgent problem in psychology. The basis of aggressive behavior is the motive of aggression. Aggression is defined as any form of behavior aimed at insulting or harming another living being in a situation where he does not want it. It requires looking at aggression not as an emotion, motive or instruction, but as a model of behavior. Aggression is a state of psychological or physical violence against another person, a mental and spiritual result of the conflict of aggressive parties, a feeling formed from the other side. Adolescence is a period of rapid and effective development of cognitive processes. The origin of aggressive behavior in teenagers is a very urgent issue. In adolescence, boys and girls have the highest and lowest levels of aggressive behavior. It has been found that aggression in boys has two transition ages: 12 years and 14-15 years. Girls also experience such a state of aggression. These processes take place between the ages of 11 and 13. For boys, it is characteristic to show aggression in a direct, open form and to the person entering into the conflict. It is characteristic of a girl to consider verbal aggression in its various forms as acceptable. In everyday life, aggression is used as a means of violence or to defeat an opponent. Aggression comes from the Latin "agressio" which means to attack. The term aggression is often associated with emotions such as anger, motives such as humiliation and harm, and even racial and ethnic differences. Aggression is a manifestation of disorders in the emotional sphere, a failure in the child's psychological protection. The development and manifestation of aggressive behavior often occurs in connection with the social environment. An aggressive teenager creates problems and difficulties not only for those around him, but also for himself. Aggressiveness in adolescents leads to physiological and psychological changes during the transition from childhood to adulthood. The main problem of adolescence is trying to see who one is not. In such cases, teenagers become aggressive. Negativism, aggression and dissatisfaction are the main signs of crisis in adolescence. A calm and obedient child in childhood becomes nervous and rude when he becomes a teenager. In this case, it is necessary to show the child the basic norms of behavior and establish positive communication in the family. Adolescents live mainly with momentary decisions. Conflicts between parents and children in the family, situations of mutual misunderstanding, failure to adopt the method of leadership in the family, and the presence of dysfunctional families cause aggression in teenagers. Most parents, instead of raising children with positive emotions, influence with force and rudeness. In turn, such behavior causes the formation of aggressive behavior in adolescents. Demonstration of aggressive situations in teenagers can mainly cause negative evaluation, conflict, pressure, damage, anger and other negative situations. Excessively aggressive children are squeezed out from their peers. In this case, the child becomes more aggressive and lonely. In this case, teenagers may commit crimes. Negativism is a normal part of child development. Negativism is observed to appear at different stages of human development. In this case, it is often observed in children in adolescence. Negativism usually appears at the age of two and lasts for several years and shows the child's independence and reappears in adolescence and begins to assert himself as a person. Negativism is clearly manifested in all areas of adolescent life. In addition, it lasts for several weeks or the teenager leaves the family for a long time. This difficult and acute course is observed in 20% of

adolescents. Negativism is manifested in adolescents' ways of ensuring independence from parents and controlling their behavior. As negativity continues to develop in teenagers, it becomes a characteristic of a person, which can be a sign of personality disorder.

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